

E-RIHS PP

CALL: H2020-INFRADEV-2016-2

TYPE OF ACTION: CSA

GA n.739503

D.8.1 Catalogue of E-RIHS resources and services

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Deliverable nature	Report (R)
Dissemination level	Public
Contractual delivery date	M30
Actual delivery date	M30
Version	1.0
Total page of number	74
Keywords	Catalogue, Conceptual Model, RDMS, Heritage Science, Cultural Heritage

Abstract

The Deliverable 8.1 describes the work carried in Task 8.3 “Catalogue of E-RIHS resources and services”. With the term *resource* we intend any entity that may be of interest to a Infrastructure such as the one that the E-RIHS PP project is setting up, *i.e.* mainly datasets and services, but also people, organizations, instruments, and other entities. The catalogue aims at providing researchers with information related to Heritage Science resources available within E-RIHS through a formal model that helps categorising them according to their different features. Such features will also be used for discovering the resources in the Catalogue.

The catalogue structure was designed to serve as the basis for accounting in-kind contributions and, in perspective, to be a single access point for resource discovery and access services.

Document information

Project number	739503	Acronym	E-RIHS PP
Full title	European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science – Preparatory Phase		
Project url	www.e-rihs.eu		
Document url			
EU Project Officer	Maria Theofilatou		

Deliverable	Number	D.8.1.	Title	Catalogue of E-RIHS resources and services
Work Package	Number	8	Title	E-RIHS services for Heritage Science scholars

Date of delivery	Contractual	M30	Actual	M30
Status	Version 1.0		<input type="checkbox"/> Draft <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Final	
Nature	<input type="checkbox"/> prototype <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> report <input type="checkbox"/> demonstrator <input type="checkbox"/> other			
Dissemination level	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public <input type="checkbox"/> restricted			

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Abstract (for dissemination)	The Deliverable 8.1 describes the work carried in Task 8.3 “Catalogue of E-RIHS resources and services” - in order to create a catalogue of E-RIHS PP resources. With the term <i>resource</i> we intend any entity that may be of interest to a digital Infrastructure such as the one that the E-RIHS PP project
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Version Log			
Issue Date	Rev. no.	Author	Change
31/01/2019	0.1	Valentina Bartalesi and Carlo Meghini	Preliminary version of the deliverable issued at M24
21/07/2020	1.0	Carlo Meghini, Valentina Bartalesi, Cesare Concordia, Laura Benassi, Marco Galeotti	Draft submitted for quality control
31/07/2020	1.1	Carlo Meghini, Valentina Bartalesi, Cesare Concordia, Laura Benassi, Marco Galeotti	Final version
10/08/2020	1.2	Jana Striova	Revision of text for before the submission

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Abbreviations

ARIADNE	The Advanced Research Infrastructure for Archaeological Dataset Networking in Europe
ACDM	ARIADNE Dataset Catalogue Model
CENDARI	Collaborative European Digital Archival Research Infrastructure
CIDOC	International Committee for Documentation
CH	Cultural Heritage
CLARIN	Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure
CP	Collaborative Projects
CRM	Conceptual Reference Model
CSA	Coordination and Support Actions
DARIAH	Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities
DCAT	Data Catalogue Vocabulary
EHRI	European Holocaust Research Infrastructure
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
IPERION CH	The Integrated Platform for the European Research Infrastructure On Cultural Heritage
IPERION HS	The Integrated Platform for the European Research Infrastructure On Heritage Science
INO	National Institute of Optics
ISTI	Istituto di Scienza e Tecnologie dell'Informazione
Huma-Num	Humanités numériques
PARTHENOS	Pooling Activities, Resources and Tools for Heritage E-research Networking, Optimization and Synergies
PEM	Parthenos Entities Model

RDBMS	Relational database management system
TGIR	Très Grande Infrastructure de Recherche

1. Introduction

The present document reports the results of Task 8.3 of the E-RIHS project, denominated “Catalogue of E-RIHS resources and services”. Task 8.3 “concerns the design, creation and maintenance of an online catalogue of resources and services provided by E-RIHS”.

Research Infrastructures provide broader access to services supporting communities of researchers in scientific discovery and collaboration across disciplinary and geographical boundaries. These services can include access to facilities, laboratories and expertise; access to and retrieval of data; cutting-edge techniques and online tools to manage and process research data. With the growth of the cultural domain, it is expected that the diversity of such services will increase. Sustainability will rely on effective trans-disciplinary communication. It is necessary to catalogue services effectively, so that users may easily satisfy their questions and information needs by consulting the Catalogue. A catalogue provides a logical organization of services used to answer the research community’s needs. A Resource Infrastructure catalogue is used to navigate and access the content of the Resource Infrastructure (taking into account the access policies of the items and organizations) and to search (keyword and faceted) and browse (by tag, organization, group, type) facilities.

Given the preparatory nature of the E-RIHS PP project, the activity of the Task has mainly been centred around an investigation on the relevant issues. In particular, the E-RIHS catalogue is based on a conceptual model that gives an account of the resources that are of interest to a digital Infrastructure such as the one that the E-RIHS PP project is setting up. Such resources include datasets and services, but also people, organizations, instruments, and other entities. Developing such conceptual model has been therefore a prerequisite to the creation of the Catalogue. Therefore, this conceptual model was implemented as a Relational Database Management System (RDBMS).

In conclusion, the E-RIHS PP catalogue aims at providing researchers with information related to Heritage Science resources available on the E-RIHS PP infrastructure through a conceptual model that helps categorising them according to their different features.

The remainder of this document is organised as follows: Section 2 reports the main requirements of the E-RIHS PP catalogue. In Section 3 we report a survey of the most important initiatives in the fields of the Heritage Science and the Humanities that have addressed, and solved, the problem of

providing a catalogue of their domain and we describe the conceptual model of the E-RIHS PP catalogue. Section 4 describes the contents of the catalogue and how they have been obtained. In Section 5 the implementation of the Catalogue as an information system is reported. In Section 6 the conclusions are drawn.

2. Requirements

The catalogue of the E-RIHS PP infrastructure should be used by different types of users with different aims in order to satisfy their information needs. Several kinds of users can be identified, from scholars to Cultural Heritage (CH) professionals - such as curators, scientists - to students and, finally, general users.

The main requirements of the E-RIHS PP catalogue that are common to all users can be summarised in the following three points:

- general exploration of the e-RIHS information space;
- discovery of services, by laboratory, by technique, by material, etc.;
- acquisition of information on services (essential characteristics, who provides the service, how the service can be accessed, what are the requirements for using the service, etc.).

In this Section, we present some use cases of how a catalogue could be used by the kinds of users reported below.

- A conservation scientist wants to know the conservation strategies (e.g. preventive conservation, curative conservation and restoration) directed at the preservation of cultural heritage collections, managed and developed by a particular institution.
- A conservation scientist wants to compare different tools that implement a particular service acquiring information about their potential results in order to choose the best for her/his aims.
- A CH scientist wants to know the types of techniques for material analysis made available by an institution in order to choose and adopt the more appropriate ones for her aims.
- A CH institution wants to publish in the infrastructure the information about the activities conducted by its laboratories. The institution can explore the catalogue to obtain an overview of the knowledge represented in it and to understand if this knowledge is sufficient

to its representational needs. If this is not sufficient, the institution can request the extension of the catalogue and consequently of the conceptual model on which the catalogue is based.

- A CH student can explore the catalogue in order to have an overview of the CH resources and to find the technical descriptions of each of them.
- A general user can explore the catalogue in order to increase her/his knowledge about particular techniques used for the treatments of a famous artwork.

We have defined these case studies to identify the operational requirements that the catalogue must satisfy. The definition of the case studies is also useful to highlight the representational requirements of the catalogue. In particular, case studies are useful for identifying the users' expectations, while helping to make recommendations for the design of a system and at the same time for developing a conceptual model to represent the collected knowledge.

3. The Conceptual Model of the resources and services Catalogue

3.1 Relevant Initiatives in Heritage Science

In order to create the E-RIHS PP conceptual model, we surveyed the most important initiatives in the fields of the Heritage Science and the Humanities that have addressed, and solved, the problem of providing a Catalogue of their domain. The objective of this investigation is twofold: (1) to collect the requirements in an implicit way, that is by looking at the solutions developed to meet these requirements, and (2) to study the solutions devised in order to reuse them as much as possible to create the E-RIHS PP catalogue.

The following projects and studies have been examined:

1. The Integrated Platform for the European Research Infrastructure On Cultural Heritage (IPERION CH) project¹ funded by the European Commission in the H2020 Programme under INFRAIA-2014-2015 - Integrating and opening existing national and regional research infrastructures of European interest, started 1st of May, 2015 and finished October 31st, 2019.
2. The Advanced Research Infrastructure for Archaeological Dataset Networking in Europe (ARIADNE) project², a combination of CP & CSA funded by the European Commission in the

¹ <http://www.iperionch.eu/>

² <http://portal.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/>

- H2020 Programme under THEME INFRA-2012-1.1.3 Research infrastructures for archaeological datasets and related technologies. Started the 1st of February, 2013 and closed on January 31st, 2017.
3. The National Heritage Science Forum Kit-Catalogue produced by the National Heritage Science Forum³, a membership organisation and registered charity committed to demonstrating the public benefit of heritage science, increasing public engagement with it and support for it.
 4. The Pooling Activities, Resources and Tools for Heritage E-research Networking, Optimization and Synergies (PARTHENOS) project⁴, funded by the European Commission in the H2020 Programme under INFRADEV-4-2014-2015 - Implementation and operation of cross-cutting services and solutions for clusters of ESFRI and other relevant research infrastructure initiatives, started the 1st of May, 2015 and due to finish October 31st, 2019.
 5. “A CIDOC CRM-based Model for the Documentation of Heritage Sciences” [Niccolucci & Felicetti, 2018] is a study that introduces an approach to the documentation of scientific data produced in heritage sciences interdisciplinary research. The study has been developed by PIN and it has been partially supported by the European Commission, projects PARTHENOS and E-RIHS PP.

Concerning IPERION CH, our investigation highlighted that a catalogue in IPERION CH had been planned but ultimately it was not produced.

The ARIADNE project aims at integrating the various data of existing archaeological research to provide the scientists powerful techniques for accessing the data and services that the research community makes available. The project developed the ARIADNE Catalogue Data Model (ACDM) [Gavrilis et al., 2015]. It describes the available resources among the various partners of the project. The catalogue is based on a data model in which the central notion of the model is the Archaeological Resource class, which has as instances the main resources categorized in:

³ <https://equipment.heritagescienceforum.org.uk/>

⁴ <https://www.parthenos-project.eu/>

- Services, representing the services owned by the ARIADNE partners and lent to the project for discovery and access;
- Language Resources, the class of all language resources described in the Catalogue. A language resource is a resource of a linguistic nature, whether in natural language or in a formal language;
- Data Resources, representing the various types of data containers owned by the ARIADNE partners and lent to the project for discovery, access and possibly integration. Data resources are categorized in collections, datasets, databases and GIS.

ACDM is an extension of the Data Catalogue Vocabulary (DCAT), a recommendation of the W3C Consortium that “is well-suited to representing government data catalogues such as Data.gov and data.gov.uk.” The DCAT Vocabulary (apart from reuse) was chosen as reference vocabulary since it is proposed as a tool for publishing datasets as Open Data. Furthermore, the ACDM is mapped to CIDOC CRM, the underlying model of the metadata repository, and the catalogue records are subsequently transformed into CIDOC CRM compatible records, enhancing the metadata repository with complementary, semantic information.

The National Heritage Science Forum Kit-Catalogues⁵ is a very simple catalogue developed in the context of the National Heritage Science Forum⁶, a UK membership organisation and registered charity committed to demonstrating the public benefit of heritage science, increasing public engagement with it and support for it. The information collected in the Kit-Catalogue is organised by Organisational Unit, e.g. British Library, Natural History Museum, National Galleries of Scotland. A complete list of the tools is reported for each organisational unit: e.g. High Resolution Digital Microscope, Multi-spectral Imaging, Stereomicroscope. The results reported in the list can be filtered by manufacturer (e.g. Leika, Bruker) or Technique (e.g. Digital microscopy, Multi-spectral imaging).

The PARTHENOS Project built on the work of ARIADNE to develop an ontology for the Catalogue of a Research Infrastructure, based on the CIDOC CRM ontology⁷. The ontology is called PARTHENOS

⁵ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat/>

⁶ <http://www.heritagescienceforum.org.uk/>

⁷ <http://cidoc-crm.org/>

Entities Model (PEM for short) and subsumes the experience of ARIADNE by refining the basic categories of the ACDM and completing it with other categories that turn out to be relevant in the infrastructural domain, such as services and software. Moreover, it can be seen as an extension of the CIDOC CRM, from which it inherits classes and properties to represent the complementary aspects. Apart from being well-founded from an ontological point of view, the PEM is also very relevant to the Cultural Heritage domain since it has been developed with the contribution of the major research infrastructures in the Humanities, as PARTHENOS is a cluster of these infrastructures. The constructs of the PEM, therefore, have been thoroughly tested by using them to model the resources of several infrastructures, as it will be noted in due course.

In addition to the project mentioned above, CNR has taken into account the study presented in “RIHS – Metadata Model for Heritage Science”. The study presents a new scientific metadata model intended to describe scientific datasets in possession of various institutions, laboratories and scientists, and concerning their archives, both the ones created during the scientific activity and the ones added at later stages. Since such activities fall within the scope of a scientific discipline (e.g. physics or chemistry) and of cultural heritage, the documentation system must draw from both. The study proposes an overarching system based on the use of CIDOC CRM and its extensions CRMsci, CRMdig and CRMpe to model physical and digital objects, events and activities, and actors, i.e. people and teams.

The model follows a modular approach (according to the CIDOC CRM conceptual principles, to which it is inspired), flexible enough to guarantee the descriptions of atomic information (single events, specific objects, single actors etc.) as well as to establish complex relationships between the various entities involved in the description of the scientific datasets. Each module focuses on the self-consistent description of each entity group in order to ensure the efficient reuse of the information and to simplify (and in many cases, to automate) the creation of rich metadata.

After examining the above initiatives, we have concluded that the work of PARTHENOS, and in particular the PEM, is the one that best fits the present E-RIHS PP catalogue purposes. Note that the services provided by the E-RIHS infrastructure are a larger set than the ones taken into account by PARTHENOS. Consequently, the PEM has to be significantly extended to fit the E-RIHS

representational requirements. Moreover, CNR has been involved in the development of the PEM and therefore is going to act as a trait-de-union between the E-RIHS and PARTHENOS catalogues.

3.2. The E-RIHS PP Conceptual Model

In order to create the E-RIHS PP catalogue, CNR chose a bottom-up approach, starting from an analysis of the available descriptions of resources. Due to the difficulty to retrieve significative number of descriptions from the institutions participating to the Task 8.1 (please, for details consult the E-RIHS PP internal report of D.8.1), CNR (ISTI-CNR) in collaboration with National Institute of Optics (INO-CNR) decided to take into account the list of resources collected within the IPERION HS project⁸. IPERION HS is a consortium of 24 partners from 23 countries that aims at creating a pan-European research infrastructure on heritage science. The infrastructure offers training and access to a wide range of high-level scientific instruments, methodologies, data and tools for advancing knowledge and innovation in heritage science. (see the following Section for details about the IPERION HS resources).

Finally, to develop the E-RIHS PP catalogue, CNR took into account the one developed within the PARTHENOS European project. The PARTHENOS catalogue is based on an ontology called Parthenos Entities Model (PEM) [Bruseker et al., 2017]. The PEM is developed using CIDOC CRM and its extension CRMdig [Doerr & Theodoridou, 2014] as reference vocabularies. The PEM has been defined starting from the analysis of the entities provided by the registries of PARTHENOS federated Digital Humanities Infrastructures - that is ARIADNE⁹ (archaeology), CENDARI¹⁰ (histor, CLARIN¹¹ (linguistic studies), CulturalItalia¹² (archaeology, arts and humanities), DARIAH¹³ (arts and humanities), EHRI¹⁴ (studies on the holocaust); TGIR Huma-Num¹⁵ (humanities and social sciences) - and it is based on five main entities:

1. Dataset is a set or collection of data, records or information that is kept as a persistent unit of information in the knowledge generation process;

⁸ <http://www.iperionhs.eu/>

⁹ <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/>

¹⁰ <http://www.cendari.eu/>

¹¹ <https://www.clarin.eu/>

¹² <http://www.culturalitalia.it/>

¹³ <http://www.dariah.eu/>

¹⁴ <https://www.ehri-project.eu/>

¹⁵ <https://www.huma-num.fr/>

2. Actor is an institution, a team or an individual person that participates in the research infrastructure as partner providing data and/or services.
3. Service is defined as the continued, declared willingness and ability of an actor to execute on demand certain activities of specific benefit to the client;
4. Software is an artefact that can be executed on a computer to perform specific operations;
5. Knowledge generation process represents the workflow of the processes used to produce specific datasets.

The PEM defines the categorical descriptions of those five entities through a minimal metadata set. It is important to note that the model does not aim at representing all aspects of the source data in the target model, but rather establish the identities of the main entities and relations between them. Taking into account the five main entities of the PEM and the available descriptions of resources collected within the IPERION HS project, CNR has defined a conceptual schema to model these resources. In particular, the E-RIHS PP conceptual model has adopted two entities of the PEM: Actor and Service. The Actor entity is represented in the E-RISH PP catalogue using two different concepts: Person and Organisational entity. The Service entity is reused in the catalogue with the same meaning as in the PEM. For what concerns the Software entity of the PEM, in our model it has been extended in order to represent all the tools of Cultural Heritage analysis. Furthermore, in comparison to the PEM main entities, we have added other four concepts in the model in order to represent all the IPERION HS resources: technique, archive, provider and platform.

In conclusion, the E-RIHS PP conceptual model is composed of the following eight main concepts:

1. Service: it describes the provided services, e.g. name, description, category of technique, technique, tool, contact person, platform
2. Person: it represents the persons involved in the management of the services, e.g. name, surname, email, phone number
3. Tool: it represents the used tools, i.e. the name, the description and the potential results of the tools
4. Technique: it describes the used techniques, e.g. the name of the technique, its description, the field of application, the material

5. Organisational entity: it represents the organisational entities that provide a service, e.g. name, acronym, legal status, address, website
6. Archive: it represents an archive, e.g. name, description, producers, dates, online inventory
7. Provider: it describes the type of providers: i.e. Main Institution, Department, Laboratory, Virtual Facility
8. Platform: it represents the three platforms ARCHLAB, FIXLAB and MOLAB of the IPERION HS project (see next Section for details), i.e. the name and the description

In addition to the main concepts listed above, the model introduces other three concepts: fields of application, type of data and materials. For each of these concepts, a list of predefined values was identified in such a way that they are used as internal vocabularies.

The field of application is related to the technique and its values are divided into two main categories: cultural heritage and natural heritage. Type of data describes the archive data and its values are divided into the following categories: publications, audio-visual material, dataset, documentation, visual materials, and not available.

Material regards both the archive data and the technique of analysis. The two main categories for this concept are: organic material and inorganic material.

This conceptual model has been implemented as a RDBMS.

4. The E-RIHS resources and services Catalogue

This Section describes the contents of the Catalogues and how they have been obtained. It consists of three sub-sections.

4.1. Data Collection Methodology

While the E-RIHS PP project was going ahead, the IPERION CH project (GA n.654028) concluded. To guarantee continuity in the provision of services, the E-RIHS community contributed to drafting the H2020 project proposal named IPERION HS (Integrating Platforms for the European Research Infrastructure on Heritage Science, now funded under the Grant Agreement n. 871034). In the last years, the E-RIHS community grew up, and the partnership became larger than expected initially. To manage the huge number of partners inside the new project, it was decided to aggregate organisations in national nodes and to ask for the support of their national coordinators to propose a coherent services' offer. Due to the complexity of the partnership and in order to avoid duplication in the services' offer, Marta Castillejo (CSIC), integration director of the E-RIHS IGOV, created a form to describe the services and asked the national coordinators to fill them in (Annex 3).

The form is composed of seven sections to collect the following data:

- Platform (FIXLAB / MOLAB / ARCHLAB)
- Name of the large/medium scale laboratory, mobile laboratory or archive
- Contact details
- Description of the Access Offer
- Previous experience of the provider in the Heritage Science
- Description of the Data Management actions to favour the integration into the future digital platform
- Other comments.

Together with the form, short guidelines were sent to the national coordinators with the criteria to describe the services. A representative sample of a form filled was sent as well.

The first collection of the forms was made via email between November 2018 and February 2019.

In total, 93 forms were filled in by the national coordinators:

- ARCHLAB 13 forms
- FIXLAB 52 forms
- MOLAB 28 forms

Figure 1 Number of the forms filled per platform (initial proposal)

Figure 2 Potential distribution of the services per country (initial proposal)

After this step, a first evaluation based on the selection criteria sent to the national coordinators was released by the platforms’ coordinators to identify the services to be included in the IPERION HS proposal. Essentially, criteria are based on the quality and unicity of the services distributed in

different countries. The criteria for selecting providers are aligned with the Quality Assessment Procedures of ERIHS PP.

The IPERION HS proposal was submitted on March 19th, 2019, approved and funded starting from April 1st, 2020. Today, the IPERION HS consortium offers transnational access through three platforms composed of 52 access facilities:

- ARCHLAB
- FIXLAB
- MOLAB.

The IPERION HS project is an opportunity to think about how to design the E-RIHS catalogue. The leading idea is to turn the information collected for IPERION HS into an experiment of the catalogue of E-RIHS's services. The online version of the IPERION HS catalogue has been planned as a model for the E-RIHS ERIC. This catalogue will be tested for three years to validate the functionality and usability for users. When E-RIHS ERIC is established, further criteria and quality controls based on excellence and unicity will be applied.

At the moment, the goal is to set up an intuitive, efficient and user-friendly catalogue for expert and non-expert users. A working group has been created to reach this goal¹⁶.

A first analysis of the catalogues of other research infrastructures has been carried out to find a good model to use. Having in mind that E-RIHS is a complex interdisciplinary research infrastructure and considering that is hard to compare E-RIHS with other projects working in completely different fields, the working group has found inspiration from the following online catalogues:

1. ELIXIR - <https://elixir-europe.org/services>
Field: *Life science*
2. EMBRC - <http://www.embrc.eu/servicerequests/exploration/explore/128#highlightCat:128>
Field: *Marine biology and ecology research*
3. CESSDA - <https://datacatalogue.cessda.eu/>
Field: *Social Science*

Before deciding on how to model data, it has been decided to adopt a double approach and design a catalogue with two types of entry-point: for expert users and non-expert users. In the first case,

¹⁶ The working group was composed of Marta Castillejo (CSIC -IQFR), Laura Benassi (CNR-INO), Marco Galeotti (CNR-INO), Elisabetta Andreassi (CNR-IBAM), Carlo Meghini (CNR-ISTI), Valentina Bartalesi (CNR-ISTI), Cesare Concordia (CNR-ISTI), Cecilia Calvo Simal (CENIEH), Jana Striova (CNR-INO).

the idea was to use an online dynamic catalogue with few filters to orienteer the search of the expert users and help them to find the right solution to specific requests. A free search field allows the expert user to find services inside the catalogue. By setting the filters, the system updates information accordingly, and the user can personalise the request.

The second approach is non-expert user-oriented to help users understand what the E-RIHS platforms are, which type of services E-RIHS offers and the potential results the user can obtain by asking for them.

After that, an accurate interpretation of the data collected in the IPERION HS forms was carried out to collect the data necessary for the database. The basic idea was to use a relational database maintaining the potentiality of the semantic data model.

Data modelling was planned jointly by CNR-INO and CNR-ISTI and new templates were created to describe (Annex 6):

- The services
- The techniques and the archives
- The tools used to perform the analysis
- People responsible for each service
- Organizations
- Location.

More details are specified in Section 4.2.

Each provider was asked to fill all the necessary templates in to describe the service/s offered.

The fields in the forms have been filled in with free text, controlled vocabularies, links and reverse links. The controlled vocabularies were built based on the following existing ones:

- RIHS “Metadata Model for Heritage Science” (lead author: Achille Felicetti)
- CIDOC CRM
- PARTHENOS Entities Minimal Metadata
- PARTHENOS Entities Model Description
- Art and Architecture Thesaurus (Getty Research Institute)

Due to the lack of consolidated ontologies and thesauri in the field of Heritage Science, partners were asked to add relevant terms to contribute to creating precise vocabularies in the catalogue. The “free search” field allows users to search specific words inside the description of the techniques and tools and improve the user experience.

A second evaluation of the services proposed by the partners was carried out in mid-April 2020 by the platforms' coordinators who defined the final list of the services (149) included in IPERION HS:

- 14 ARCHLAB archives
- 87 FIXLAB techniques
- 48 MOLAB techniques.

The following table summarises the number of templates collected to create the final version of the IPERION HS catalogue of services:

	ARCHLAB	FIXLAB	MOLAB	Total
Provider	28	53	35	116
Person	15	49	23	87
Location	-	-	-	89
Archive	14			14
Technique	-	87	48	135
Tool	-	75	47	122
				563

Table 1 Total number of templates filled in to describe the services

To ensure the quality of the data collected, all the templates have been checked, integrated and revised at different times by the providers and the platforms' coordinators to:

- Clean the data
- Standardize the data processing
- Reduce redundancy
- Validate the consistency of the data
- Enhance data integrity.

Figure 3 Distribution of the services in IPERION HS (final proposal)

Figure 4 Comparison of the services per platform in IPERION HS (light and dark blue services accepted vs. offered to the catalogue)

Figure 5 Comparison with the initial proposal per country (light and dark blue services accepted vs. offered to the catalogue)

4.2. Dataset Creation

The IPERION HS catalogue of services has been stored on MySQL Community version (<https://www.mysql.com/products/community/>) as RDBMS, an open-source relational database management system, and it is integrated into the IPERION HS website (www.iperionhs.eu), developed with the open-source tool WordPress.

We have chosen a relational database to organise the data collected during the activities carried out along the past year of the project across Europe, because the amount of data was not so high to justify a more complex topology as the ones usually present in the triplestore or RDF store structure. Furthermore, no semantics features are requested at the moment and no future integration of the database are foreseen. The objective of the collection of data was and is to present to the research community the Catalogue of Services of E-RIHS so to enable the submission of a proposal to obtain access to the facilities of the infrastructure.

For the time being, the submission of the proposals will be allowed through the IPERION HS portal that will present all the services in e-commerce style to put the services in cart, fill in a web-based template and submit the proposal using an order form.

The typical relational model organizes data into tables of columns and rows, with a unique key identifying each row. Each table represents an entity type like Service or Technique in our case. Rows are also called records or n-uples and represent instances of that type of entity. Columns are also called attributes. Hence, each table stores all the available instances of a specific entity with the values of all the attributes which participate to characterize the entity.

The data model has been realized firstly in the UML modelling language and secondly as ER complex model using the features of MySQL Workbench. (<https://www.mysql.com/products/workbench/>). The ER schema produced by CNR-INO in collaboration with CNR-ISTI is here below.

To move towards the MySQL scheme, we decided to create entity type also for some attributes which were complex by definition. A complex attribute is a type of attribute in a database and is formed by nesting composite attributes and multi-valued attributes in an arbitrary way. That was the case of the attribute “Field of application” for example. That was also the case of the attribute Material, both part of the characterization of the entity Technique.

That has been necessary in particular for mapping the characteristics of Techniques. The relational model itself imposes no order on the attributes, and an order would have not been of any importance in our case because during the presentation phase of data by specifying queries, which use operations such as select to identify tuples and join to combine relations, the attributes are adjusted as needed.

For what concern the two attributes mentioned above, namely “Field of application” and “Material”, we have chosen to define two different controlled vocabularies from the get-go, trying to restrain the number of possible outputs of our activity of gathering information from all the national providers of services. However, given the complexity of the heritage science research community, made of a huge number of scientific disciplines ranging from STEM’s like physics and chemistry to SSH’s like archeology, paleontology, just to name a few, we just let them free to add new items not already belonging to the original controlled vocabulary.

Finally, the MySQL ER model of the IPERION HS Catalogue of Services is the following:

However, because the implementation in MySQL Workbench of the ER schema is not a full implementation of the relationship model, that mainly because MySQL does not support table inheritance or multi-valued attributes, the only way to approximate that characteristic is by using foreign keys. In this respect, we have used a lot of foreign keys to express inheritance and along with some triggers to guarantee data integrity. In other cases, we preferred to create brand new tables to embed the relation between two tables or entities.

The pivotal entity in the data model is the entity “Service” that composes the complex composition of the service that will be provided to the final user in all its attributes.

In particular, the service entity is composed of the following attributes:

- Category of technique
- Technique
- Tool
- Provider
- Platform
- Contact persons

For what concerns the categorization of the analysis carried out during the access providing, that is made clear her below.

The “technical sheet” template contains data related to:

- Category of technique
- Technique / Archive
- Tool
 - Name
 - Description
 - Potential results
 - Provider (with the link to the “provider” webpage)
 - Contact person
- Related entities
 - Materials
 - Fields of application

- Helpdesk contacts
- Map/s of the provider/s
- References

To grant access to the data to the Wordpress interface, we decided not to use stored procedures for increasing the security, as it is very often done, because the copy of the database used to update data is off-line and once in a while a dump of it is loaded into the production replica of the database.

4.3. Overview of the content of the E-RIHS resources and services Catalogue [INO, ISTIJ]

For what concern the contents of the Catalogue, namely the instances stored in it, we present here below some diagrams about the composition of data in terms of country, technique and service provided.

Figure 6 a bar chart showing number of Services by Country

It is interesting to underscore how heterogenous is the composition of the Catalogue and how high is the rate of services provided by each country on average.

E-RIHS has been accepted into the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructure (ESFRI) 2016 Roadmap, to spur social and cultural innovation. E-RIHS PP (Preparation Phase) partnership

joins 16 countries (15 EU Member States plus Israel), 2 ERICs and 3 institutions representing scientific communities. E-RIHS PP also counts 6 observers and involves over 100 heritage science institutions worldwide. Amongst its services, E-RIHS ERIC will provide access to a wide range of cutting-edge scientific infrastructures, methodologies, data and tools. It will also provide training, remote and virtual access to its facilities. In addition, E-RIHS is already present in US and LAC with the intent to expand the infrastructure at a global level.

Figure 7 a bar chart showing number of Services by Category of Technique

In terms of the number of categories, it would be great if in the near future this number could be reduced to embrace a more compact and accessible picture of the heritage science sector in terms of analysis that which could be performed on an artefact. There is, in fact, an issue in terms of the accessibility to the tools that the infrastructure makes available to the kind of researchers that come from the SSH area of knowledge. Often, it’s clear what type of results or indications it would be needed to finish up a heritage science project, but less often researchers know which kind of tool or technique they need to apply for. However, we have tried already at this stage to uniform as much as possible technique and tool in agreement with the service providers reaching a compromise between the rigour of the scientific techniques’ taxonomy and the needs of the communication efforts.

Figure 8 a bar chart showing number of Services by Facility

5. The Implementation of the Catalogue Service [INO]

The IPERION HS catalogue of services has been stored on MySQL Community version (<https://www.mysql.com/products/community/>), an open-source relational database management system, and it is integrated into the IPERION HS website (www.iperionhs.eu), created with the open-source tool WordPress.

The relational database organises the data collected into 31 customized tables. The data model has been realized firstly in the UML modelling language and secondly as an ER complex model using the features of MySQL Workbench. (<https://www.mysql.com/products/workbench/>).

The MySQL model of the IPERION HS Catalogue of Services is the following:

Figure 9 MySQL model of the IPERION HS catalogue of services

The pivotal entity in the data model is the entity “Service” that composes the complex composition of the service that will be provided to the final user in all its attributes. In particular, the service entity is composed of the following attributes:

- Category of technique
- Technique

- Tool
- Provider
- Platform
- Contact persons.

For what concerns the categorization of the analysis carried out during the access providing, that is made clear here below.

The “technical sheet” template contains data related to:

- Category of technique
- Technique / Archive
- Tool
 - Name
 - Description
 - Potential results
 - Provider (with the link to the “provider” webpage)
 - Contact person
- Related entities
 - Materials
 - Fields of application
 - Helpdesk contacts
 - Map/s of the provider/s
 - References

FIXLAB > Category: Accelerated Ageing tests
Zooarchaeology

Study of animal remains from archaeological sites in order to understand how people used and interacted with animals in the past, the environments people lived in, created and changed, and their effect on animal biodiversity and biogeography.

Fields of application

- Cultural heritage**
archaeological object and site, anthropogenic object
- Natural heritage**
animal product, shell, skeleton

Materials

- organic**
animal parts

TOOLS

FIXLAB
 @ TOOL • ACCELERATED AGEING TESTS
 Skeleton preparation facility

The skeleton preparation facilities include all equipment necessary for defleshing and degreasing animal skeletons from horse size to small birds, to a required standard. The facilities include three large freezers and a fridge. Two induction heaters (hobs) and suitable pots are used for simmering and boiling, and a temperature probe can be used to maintain...

Provider: [Heritage Science Laboratory](#) Contact person: [Polydora Baker](#)

Provider
Heritage Science Laboratory
 Fort Cumberland Road - PO4 9LD Portsmouth United Kingdom

- Reference**
- <https://historicensland.org.uk/research/methods/archaeology/zooarchaeology/>
 - <https://historicensland.org.uk/images-books/publications/animal-bones-and-archaeology/>
 - <https://equipment.heritagescienceforum.org.uk/>

Figure 10 Screenshot of the catalogue (technique)

FIXLAB > Category: Accelerated Ageing tests

Technique: Zooarchaeology
Skeleton preparation facility

The skeleton preparation facilities include all equipment necessary for defleshing and degreasing animal skeletons from horse size to small birds, to a required standard. The facilities include three large freezers and a fridge. Two induction heaters (hobs) and suitable pots are used for simmering and boiling, and a temperature probe can be used to maintain water at a constant temperature. A modified incubator is available where required for enzyme treatment. We can also provide courses in skeleton preparation, including carcass identification and recording, skinning, defleshing, treatment with enzymes

Potential Results

Curation and development of skeletal collections

Provider

Figure 11 Screenshot of the catalogue (tool)

The system has a counter to count the requests for each tool. Those numbers will be useful to monitor the KPIs and to gather together the statistics for the periodic reports of the project and for other statistical purposes of the future E-RIHS ERIC infrastructure.

The “provider” template contains the following information:

- Name
- Description
- Contact person/s

The catalogue is composed of a list of techniques and related searchable through some filters:

- Platform
- Categories of technique
- Country
- Full-Text search. This type of search finds data in all the fields of the database.

CATALOGUE

The screenshot displays the E-RIHS catalogue interface. On the left side, there are several filter menus: Platform (set to MOLAB), Technique Category (set to View all), Technique (set to View all), Country (set to View all), and a Search input field. A 'Clear All' button is located below the search field. On the right side, the search results are displayed under the filter 'Platform: MOLAB'. Two results are shown, both under the category '2D/3D ANALYSIS'. The first result is for 'TOOL: 3D STRUCTURE-LIGHT SCANNER AND 3D LASER SCANNERS SYSTEM', with a description: '3D structure-light scanner: works with white light and does not acquire colour information. It is equipped with a CMOS 5 Megapixel camera and three different sets of lenses. The S60, with a field of view of 49x40mm and a maximum...'. The provider is 'Science and Technology in Archaeology and Culture Research Center' and the country is 'Cyprus'. The second result is for 'TOOL: ACOUSTIC TOMOGRAPHY MODULE', with a description: 'Acoustic tomography module includes the pulser/receiver system (400 MHz frequency) that stimulates the piezoelectric transducer element (frequencies from 15 to 250 MHz) to excite the high...'. Both results include a shopping cart icon.

Figure 12 Screenshot of the catalogue (filters on the left)

In the catalogue, the user can ask for a “service”. A service is always composed of four elements: technique, tool, category of technique and provider.

To ask for a service, the user needs to register in the IPERION HS website. Once logged in, the user can put a service in the cart.

The original idea was to optimise the user experience by creating an online catalogue similar to those of the main e-commerce companies. The user does not have to learn anything new. The idea of a cart is born according to this philosophy. The user can put one or more archives or tools in the cart and write a proposal for each platform. At the moment, it is not possible to write a proposal containing tools or archives belonging to different platforms at the same time but this could be probably implemented in the future. Each platform has a specific online application form, and it is not possible to mix together.

The application form is divided into 5 main sections:

1. Title and acronym of the proposal
2. User Group Leader information
3. Other user/s involved in the proposal (repeater field)
4. Scientific and technical description
5. Terms and conditions.

In the “Scientific and technical description”, the user is required to upload a pdf file containing the core proposal filled in according to the provided template.

The user can save a draft of the proposal and submit it once ready. Once the proposal has been submitted, an automatic email with a link is sent to the user. The user has to click on the link to activate the evaluation procedure. To this purpose, a custom post type on WordPress will be created, and an email will be sent to the contact person of the provider linked to the proposal.

5.1 The IPERION HS dashboards system

A system of dashboards has been created to facilitate the proposals management. There are four dashboards for:

1. The user (who submits the proposal)
2. The contact person of the facility/provider (who offers access to techniques and tools selected in the proposal)
3. The platforms’ coordinators (who centrally manage the access to a specific platform)

4. The central User Helpdesk (who overviews access in all the three platforms) and central project office in charge of submitting the project report to EC

The last three dashboards are connected hierarchically with different roles of management.

Figure 13 Hierarchy of the dashboards

The flux diagram representing the process that the system of dashboards manages is shown in Figure 14 below. This flow recalls very closely the typical editorial management flow of article approval. The article should pass from the first status (the submission of the proposal in our case) to the approval from the editor in chief. Equally, in E-RIHS there are two layers of approval and one layer of evaluation for each proposal. All this status needs to be passed to reach the final approval that guarantees the access provision.

Figure 14 Flux diagram of the dashboard

All the dashboards are provided with an alert system, set up to understand if there is something to do or not immediately:

- **Green** - everything is right, there is nothing to do (e.g. the proposal is feasible; in case of multi-analysis proposal, the analysis can pass through the PRP; in case the whole proposal pass the PRP evaluation and is inserted in the main list, the contact person can arrange the access with the user group leader)
- **Yellow** - there is something to do or check (e.g. the multi-analysis proposal is partially feasible)
- **Red** - something went wrong or a proposal is not feasible temporarily or definitively
- **Blue** - access carried and proposal archived.

In the dashboards, the status of the proposal can change from:

- **Submitted** - The status changes automatically when the proposal is submitted by the user. A confirmation email is sent to the user and the contact person of the facility/provider.
- **Feasible, Unfeasible, Partially feasible** - This status depends on the evaluation of the contact person of the facility/provider. An email is sent to the platform coordinator.
- **Reviewed** - This status is changed by the platform coordinator once the Peer Review Panel has reviewed the proposal.
- **Main List, Reserve List, Below threshold** - Once approved, the Platform Coordinator changes the status accordingly with the rankings. At this point, an automatic email informs the user about the results of the evaluation.
- **Carried out** - This status is active when the contact person of the facility/provider assesses that the access has been carried out. At this point, an automatic email is sent to the user asking for post access duties.
- **Close** - When all the contact persons related to a specific proposal assesses that the access has been carried out, the status changes automatically into “close”.
- **Archive** - When a proposal is close, the platform coordinator can archive it. By that time, the proposal will be visible in the archive of each dashboard.

5.1.1 Dashboard of the user

Once submitted a proposal, the user can check its status and manage the “post access duties” in the personal dashboard:

The screenshot shows the IPERION HS User Dashboard. At the top, there are navigation links: PROFILE, DASHBOARD, and CART. Below this is a dark blue header with the IPERION HS logo and a menu with items: ABOUT, SERVICES, TRAINING, NEWS, HIGHLIGHTS, PUBLICATIONS, GALLERY, and CONTACTS. The main content area starts with a link to 'Go to the Archive' and a welcome message: 'Welcome to the IPERION HS User Dashboard. Here you can check the status of your proposal, upload the "User report" and inform the User Helpdesk about the fulfilment of the post access duties. If you click on the ID of your proposal/s, you can review what you have submitted. When your access experience is over, you can go to the archive and download your application.'

ID	TITLE	CREATED AT	SERVICES	POST ACCESS DUTIES	CLOSING DATE OF THE CALL	STATUS
fix_2	EMPTY	2020-07-15 15:08:02	Particle Induced Gamma-ray Emission (PIGE) HU2	<input type="checkbox"/> I have submitted the EU survey <input type="checkbox"/> I have submitted the Satisfaction Survey of Platform <input type="button" value="Submit"/> Upload final report: <input type="button" value="Choose file"/> No file chosen <input type="button" value="Upload file"/>	EMPTY	<input type="button" value="SUBMITTED"/>

Figure 15 Screenshot of the dashboard of the user

5.1.2 Dashboard of the contact person of the facility/provider

Once received the email and logged in the “facility” dashboard, the contact person of the facility/provider can see the proposal.

Figure 16 Screenshot of the dashboard of the contact person

The contact person can see the following data:

- ID of the proposal - it is composed of the three letters of the platform (ARC, FIX, MOL) + a counter for each platform. Clicking on the ID, it is possible to open the proposal and check all the data inserted;
- Service name
- Email of the user
- Type of proposal (new, continuation, resubmission)
- Date of the creation of the proposal
- Feasibility - the contact person assesses the feasibility or unfeasibility of the analysis/analyses requested to its facility
- Access carried out - here the contact person assesses that the access has been carried out
- Comments - this field allows the contact person of the facility/provider to leave comments about the feasibility or unfeasibility of the proposal. These comments can be read by the platform coordinator and the User Helpdesk.
- Status of the proposal - the status changes accordingly to the advancement of the evaluation process.

The contact person must evaluate the feasibility of the proposal. The feasibility is an evaluation that considers mainly technical issues.

If the analysis is feasible, the contact person clicks on “yes” in the dashboard and an email to the platform’s coordinator is sent to warn about the fact and invite to send the proposal to the Peer Review Panel for the scientific evaluation.

If one or more analyses are not feasible, the following situations can happen:

- If it is a single analysis proposal, the proposal turns into the “unfeasible” status
- If it is a multi-analyses proposal, the proposal becomes “partially feasible”. “Partially feasible” means that some analyses are feasible and some are not. This status requires that the facility contacts the user asking for more information or integration. At this point, the proposal can be turned into:
 - Feasible - if the problem of the unfeasibility can be solved completely. In this case, the contact person of the facility/provider must ask the platform coordinator for overriding the role and changing the status from “unfeasible” to “feasible”.
 - Partially feasible - If the problem of the unfeasibility can be solved partially, the facility asks the User Helpdesk to go to the backend of the IPERION HS website, clone the application of the user and asks the user to go to the personal dashboard to remove the unfeasible analysis and modify the proposal accordingly to the suggestion of the User Helpdesk. In the personal dashboard, the user finds the proposal already pre-filled with the previous data. The user can remove the unfeasible analysis, add another analysis if necessary, save the draft and submit the proposal again. At this point, a new version of the proposal starts a new evaluation process. In case this change is required after the deadline of the call, the proposal maintains the date of the first submission.
 - Unfeasible - when it is not possible to solve the unfeasibility.

5.1.3 Dashboard of the platform coordinator

The platform coordinator can check the activities related to all the proposals submitted to the related platform.

ID	TITLE	USER	TYPE OF PROPOSAL	FACILITY	CONTACTS PERSON	CREATED	NUMBER CALL	PROPOSAL STATUS	ALERT
fix_4	test fixlab net7	baroncini+1234@netseven.it	New	BioArCh Heritage Science Laboratory	nathan.wales@york.ac.uk polydora.baker@HistoricEngland.org.uk	2020-07-16 10:39:21	3	PARTIALLY_FEASIBLE	●
fix_2	test fixlab	baroncini+1234@netseven.it	New	Heritage Macromolecular Laboratory	polona.ropret@zvkd.si	2020-07-15 11:36:47	3	SUBMITTED	●
fix_1	test fixlab	baroncini+1234@netseven.it	New	Budapest Neutron Center	szenmiklosi.laszlo@energia.mta.hu	2020-07-15 10:30:50	3	SUBMITTED	●

Figure 17 Screenshot of the dashboard of the platform coordinator (FIXLAB)

In the dashboard, the platform coordinator has additional information on the proposal and the activity of the contact persons. In particular, the platform coordinator can:

- Check the proposal clicking on the ID and change the feasibility of the proposal on request of the contact person of the facility/provider
- Read and download all the files uploaded by the user (pdf, jpeg, etc..)
- Verify the facility/ies involved in the proposal
- Verify the closing date and the number of the call
- Verify the status of the proposal and change as requested

5.1.4. Dashboard of the User Helpdesk

The dashboard of the User Helpdesk gives a general overview of all the proposals submitted to all the three platforms.

ID	TITLE	USER	TYPE OF PROPOSAL	FILES	FACILITY	CONTACTS PERSON	CREATED AT	CLOSING CALL DATE	NUMBER CALL	STATUS	ALERT
mol_1	test irena	irenedelgratta5@gmail.com	New	heritage-science-1-pdf	Science and Technology in Archaeology and Culture Research Center	n.bakirtzis@cyl.ac.cy	2020-07-14 11:20:09	EMPTY	EMPTY	SUBMITTED	●
fix_2	EMPTY	laura.benassi@cnr.it	New	d2-2-e-rihs-quality-manual-and-kpi9-pdf	Ion Beams Laboratory	szikszai.zita@mta.ATOMKI.hu	2020-07-15 15:06:02	EMPTY	EMPTY	SUBMITTED	●
fix_3	aereg	baroncini+12345678@netseven.it	New	description_of_project-4-pdf	FORTH - Institute of Electronic Structure and Laser BioArCh	ppouli@iesl.forth.gr nathan.wales@york.ac.uk	2020-07-24 10:38:42	2020-09-01 00:00:00	1	PARTIALLY_FEASIBLE	●
fix_4	aereg 2	baroncini+12345678@netseven.it	New	description_of_project-4-pdf	BioArCh	nathan.wales@york.ac.uk	2020-07-24 10:54:18	EMPTY	EMPTY	SUBMITTED	●

Figure 18 Screenshot of the dashboard of the User Helpdesk

The User Helpdesk can:

- Read and download all the files uploaded by the users

- Close the access procedure after the user has carried out the post access duties.

The User Helpdesk can order the information by filters (platform, data, call).

5.2 Data Analytics tool

The dashboard of the User Helpdesk will be implemented with an online tool for data analytics, such as Qlik. The tool will be very useful to elaborate general statistics and make an identikit of the typical user, based on the following data:

- Type of proposal
- Number of applicants
- Family Name and First Name
- Nationality
- Birth year
- Gender
- Home Institution
- City
- HI Legal Status Code
- HI Country CODE
- Function/job/Title
- Academic background
- Position Code
- Scientific Discipline of the project proposal.

Statistics will not analyse sensitive data.

5.3 The User experience in designing the IPERION HS catalogue

The catalogue of IPERION HS has been designed as a user-centered tool. A user experience test was planned to have a deeper understanding of the needs and behavior of the typical user of IPERION HS services.

The “catalogue system” is composed of four main elements:

1. Catalogue of services - the core catalogue with a description of techniques, tools and providers

2. Registration form - it is required to register in the system to submit a project proposal
3. Online application form - it is the form to fill in when a user asks for accessing the IPERION HS services
4. Dashboard - it is a tool to manage the project proposals submitted.

Taking into consideration the knowledge and experience collected during the transnational access in the previous EU project (CHARISMA GA n. 228330 and IPERION CH GA n.654028), the working group has focused the planning and testing process on improving the quality of the user's interaction with the catalogue system. The main objective is to make the user experience easy and fruitful.

The initial idea was to find the best combination and visualisation of elements to facilitate the user in browsing the catalogue, find the appropriate resources and submit a project proposal.

The result is the balance between what the working group has planned and what the project constraints allow including factors as the budget, time availability, information availability, etc.

The system has passed through two phases:

1. Design phase
2. Validation phase.

During the first phase, the working group has manipulated and organized data to make information useful, usable, findable, accessible. The strength of this project has been to know the user needs in the initial phase. Starting from them, the system has been designed following the consolidated User Interface principles with precise information architecture, content strategy, content requirements, navigation design, visual design.

In the second phase, the working group has planned the usability evaluation together with testers. The working group asked providers, platform coordinators and potential users for testing the beta version of the "catalogue system". The users have been chosen with different backgrounds, expertise and provenance, preferring non-expert users.

The usability test has considered the following elements:

- Intuitive design - how the catalogue, the registration form, the application form and the dashboards are easy to use
- Ease of learning - how fast a user who has never asked for access before can fulfil basic tasks
- Efficiency of use - how fast an experienced user can fulfil tasks

- Error frequency and severity - how often users make errors while using the catalogue system and how users recover from the errors
- Subjective satisfaction - if the users appreciate the catalogue system as a whole.

The tests on the catalogue have been conducted in two ways:

1. The working group has conducted an online testing exercise together with the platform coordinators and the providers and noted the comments in a file
2. Testers have used the catalogue on their own, noted their comments and sent them by email.

Basing the test on the above elements, testers were asked for noting each difficulty encountered in understanding and using the catalogue, the registration form, the online application form, the dashboard.

During the beta test, comments from the testers were collected and divided into categories:

- Catalogue (content, readability, the correctness of data, visualisation, etc.)
- Registration (ease-to-use, the time required for filling it in, functioning, fairness, ...)
- Application form (ease-to-use, the time required for filling it in, data required, fairness, etc.)
- Dashboards (ease-to-understand, ease-to-use, clarity, efficiency, etc.)

All the tests were very useful to improve the usability of the “catalogue system” and understand the strong and weak points. Most of the improvements have been already implemented.

A re-testing of the catalogue has been performed with few persons to measure the effectiveness of the changes applied.

The final version of the online catalogue has been released on July 31th 2020 and it is available at: <http://www.iperionhs.eu/access-to-facilities/>.

6. Conclusions

The present document reports the results of Task 8.3 of the E-RIHS project, denominated “Catalogue of E-RIHS resources and services”. Task 8.3 “concerns the design, creation and maintenance of an online catalogue of resources and services provided by E- RIHS”.

The E-RIHS PP catalogue aims at providing researchers with information related to Heritage Science resources available within the E-RIHS infrastructure. These resources include datasets and services, but also people, organizations, instruments, techniques, and other entities. The Catalogue allows users of the E-RIHS infrastructure to discover these resources, acquire information about them and, where possible, to access them.

Given the preparatory nature of the E-RIHS PP project, the activity of the Task has mainly been centered around an investigation on the relevant issues and the development of a demonstrator on a sample set of data and a specific set of requirements. The core element of the demonstrator is a conceptual model of the above-mentioned resources and an implementation of this model based on a Relational Database Management System (RDBMS) where the data are persisted to be used by the functions implementing the services on them.

The requirements are presented in Section 2, while Section 3 gives a survey of the most important initiatives in the fields of the Heritage Science and the Humanities that have addressed, and solved, the problem of providing a catalogue within their domain and we describe the conceptual model of the E-RIHS PP catalogue. Section 4 describes the contents of the catalogue and how they have been obtained. In Section 5 the implementation of the Catalogue as an information system is reported. Some useful technical material is provided in the Appendices.

Based on the experience of previous projects on the development of a Research Infrastructure, the construction, maintenance, and regular update of a Catalogue requires a powerful separated IT infrastructure, known as *Aggregation Infrastructure*, whose main task is to collect the data about resources from the community members, transform these data into a common format based on an ontology, and integrate them into the information space of the target Research Infrastructure. The set-up and operation of such an Aggregation Infrastructure requires a collective effort and an amount of resources that largely exceeds those of Task 8.3 of E-RIHS, and must be carefully prepared

and planned. The activity of this Task and the results presented in this Deliverable are meant to provide useful inputs to the preparation and planning of a Catalogue for the future E-RIHS.

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Appendix

Annex 1. The Catalogue Software System

A more detailed description of the methods and technologies used for the implementation of the Catalogues, including software licences and screenshots of the GUIs.

Annex 2. The Catalogue Database

Figure 19 A diagram showing the complete SQL schema of the IPERION HS database

Figure 20 A diagram showing the SQL schema for the main tables of the IPERION HS database

Some simple queries have been developed to compare the data gathered with the data as modeled in the MySQL RBMS.

The most important is the following:

```

SELECT se.Service_id, pr.Provider_id, pr.Facility, cot.Cat_technique_id, se.contact_person1,
pe.name, pe.surname ,o4.acronym as 'FacilityName',
cot.`short name` as 'Cat of Techn',
tec.Technique_id, tec.name as 'technique', tool.idtool, tool.name as 'tool',
se.Analysis_name, se.Platform_IdPlatform
FROM
nuovo.Service se, nuovo.Provider pr,

```

```
nuovo.Category_of_technique as cot,  
nuovo.Technique as tec,  
nuovo.Organizational_entity as o4,  
nuovo.Tool as tool,  
nuovo.Person as pe
```

WHERE

```
pr.Provider_id=se.id_provider and  
cot.Cat_technique_id=se.id_CatTechnique  
and tec.Technique_id=se.technique  
and tool.idtool=se.tool  
and o4.Organizational_entity_id =pr.facility  
and pe.Person_id=se.contact_person1  
order by `FacilityName`;
```

It permits to have a clear and immediate view of all the instances of the services stored in the database with the values of the main attributes on the screen.

Annex 3. Form used to collect information on the services during the IPERION HS proposal’s drafting

<p>DESCRIPTION OF ACCESS OFFER FOR IPERION HS PROPOSAL</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> FIXLAB/<input type="checkbox"/> MOLAB/<input type="checkbox"/> ARCHLAB</p> <p>Select the platform and fill one questionnaire per each type of access offer</p>
<p>Name of the large/medium scale laboratory, mobile laboratory or archive</p> <p>Country of the National Node</p>
<p>Contact details</p>
<p>Name of the large/medium scale laboratory, mobile laboratory or archive:</p> <p>Contact person:</p> <p>e-mail:</p> <p>phone number:</p>
<p>Description of the Access Offer</p>
<p>General description and uniqueness of the access offer</p>
<p>Applications to different types of materials or heritage objects, and information that can be obtained (for FIXLAB/MOLAB), or</p> <p>Content and related type of objects/collection materials (for ARCHLAB)</p>
<p>Description of the characteristics of the equipment/s, applicable for FIXLAB/MOLAB</p>
<p>Selected bibliography about the technique(s) or method (FIXLAB and MOLAB) or related to the resources available (ARCHLAB) published by the provider (up to 5 references)</p>
<p>Previous experience of the provider in the Heritage Science</p>
<p>General description of the team and its experience</p>
<p>Previous national and international projects on Heritage Science involving the proposed access offer</p>
<p>Selected publications by the provider (up to 5 references)</p>
<p>Number of requests of transnational access foreseen per year (based on past experience of the provider if applicable)</p>
<p>Describe data management actions you will implement in favour of an integration into the future digital platform</p>
<p>Other comments</p>
<p><input type="checkbox"/> I hereby authorize the use of my personal data in accordance to the GDPR 679/16 - "European regulation on the protection of personal data".</p>

Annex 4. SQL create DB script

```

SET @OLD_UNIQUE_CHECKS=@@UNIQUE_CHECKS, UNIQUE_CHECKS=0;
SET @OLD_FOREIGN_KEY_CHECKS=@@FOREIGN_KEY_CHECKS, FOREIGN_KEY_CHECKS=0;
SET @OLD_SQL_MODE=@@SQL_MODE, SQL_MODE='ONLY_FULL_GROUP_BY,STRICT_TRANS_TABLES,NO_ZERO_IN_DATE,NO_ZERO_DATE,ERROR_FOR_DIVISION_BY_ZERO,NO_ENGINE_SUBSTITUTION';

-----
-- Schema erihS
-----
CREATE SCHEMA IF NOT EXISTS `erihS` DEFAULT CHARACTER SET utf8 ;
USE `erihS` ;

-----
-- Table `erihS`.`Archive`
-----
CREATE TABLE IF NOT EXISTS `erihS`.`Archive` (
  `Archive_id` INT NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `title` VARCHAR(128) NOT NULL COMMENT 'title is the original name in the local language of the archive',
  `title_en` VARCHAR(128) NULL COMMENT 'title_en is the English name of the archive',
  `acronym` VARCHAR(128) NULL,
  `type` VARCHAR(45) NULL COMMENT 'Type can be only: Physical archive, Digital archive, Both',
  `description` VARCHAR(8192) NULL COMMENT 'Detailed description of the archive. The length has to be decided.',
  `producer_subjects` VARCHAR(1024) NULL COMMENT 'the subject who produces the archival documentation',
  `archival_dates` VARCHAR(256) NULL COMMENT 'Date of the documentation preserved in the archive - exact dates (1970-1992), open date (1970-), centuries (19th)',
  `online inventory` VARCHAR(128) NULL,
  `other online resources` VARCHAR(256) NULL,
  `keywords` VARCHAR(256) NULL,
  `notes` VARCHAR(2048) NULL COMMENT 'it includes some possible limitation/warning that could be relevant somehow',
  `Archive_type_idArchive_type` INT NOT NULL,
  `Provider_idProvider` INT NOT NULL,
  `Platform_idPlatform` INT NOT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`Archive_id`, `Archive_type_idArchive_type`, `Platform_idPlatform`),
  CONSTRAINT `fk_Archive_Archive_type1`
    FOREIGN KEY (`Archive_type_idArchive_type`)
    REFERENCES `erihS`.`Archive_type` (`idArchive_type`)
    ON DELETE NO ACTION
    ON UPDATE NO ACTION,
  CONSTRAINT `fk_Archive_Provider1`
    FOREIGN KEY (`Provider_idProvider`)
    REFERENCES `erihS`.`Provider` (`Provider_id`)
    ON DELETE NO ACTION

```

```

    ON UPDATE NO ACTION,
CONSTRAINT `fk_Archive_Platform1`
    FOREIGN KEY (`Platform_idPlatform`)
    REFERENCES `erihis`.`Platform` (`Platform_id`)
    ON DELETE NO ACTION
    ON UPDATE NO ACTION)
ENGINE = InnoDB;
CREATE INDEX `fk_Archive_Archive_type1_idx` ON `erihis`.`Archive` (`Archive_type_idArchive_type` ASC) VISIBLE;
CREATE INDEX `fk_Archive_Provider1_idx` ON `erihis`.`Archive` (`Provider_idProvider` ASC) VISIBLE;
CREATE INDEX `fk_Archive_Platform1_idx` ON `erihis`.`Archive` (`Platform_idPlatform` ASC) VISIBLE;
-----
-- Table `erihis`.`Archive_has_Competence`
-----
CREATE TABLE IF NOT EXISTS `erihis`.`Archive_has_Competence` (
  `Archive_idArchive` INT NOT NULL,
  `Competence_idCompetence` INT NOT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`Archive_idArchive`, `Competence_idCompetence`),
  CONSTRAINT `fk_Archive_has_Competence_Archive1`
    FOREIGN KEY (`Archive_idArchive`)
    REFERENCES `erihis`.`Archive` (`Archive_id`)
    ON DELETE NO ACTION
    ON UPDATE NO ACTION,
  CONSTRAINT `fk_Archive_has_Competence_Competence1`
    FOREIGN KEY (`Competence_idCompetence`)
    REFERENCES `erihis`.`Competence` (`Competence_id`)
    ON DELETE NO ACTION
    ON UPDATE NO ACTION)
ENGINE = InnoDB;
CREATE INDEX `fk_Archive_has_Competence_Competence1_idx` ON `erihis`.`Archive_has_Competence`
(`Competence_idCompetence` ASC) VISIBLE;
CREATE INDEX `fk_Archive_has_Competence_Archive1_idx` ON `erihis`.`Archive_has_Competence` (`Archive_idArchive` ASC)
VISIBLE;
-----
-- Table `erihis`.`Archive_has_Language`
-----
CREATE TABLE IF NOT EXISTS `erihis`.`Archive_has_Language` (
  `Archive_idArchive` INT NOT NULL,
  `Archive_Archive_type_idArchive_type` INT NOT NULL,
  `Language_idLanguage` INT NOT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`Archive_idArchive`, `Archive_Archive_type_idArchive_type`, `Language_idLanguage`),
  CONSTRAINT `fk_Archive_has_Language_Archive1`
    FOREIGN KEY (`Archive_idArchive`, `Archive_Archive_type_idArchive_type`)

```

```

REFERENCES `erihis`.`Archive` (`Archive_id`, `Archive_type_idArchive_type`)
ON DELETE NO ACTION
ON UPDATE NO ACTION,
CONSTRAINT `fk_Archive_has_Language_Language1`
FOREIGN KEY (`Language_idLanguage`)
REFERENCES `erihis`.`Language` (`Language_id`)
ON DELETE NO ACTION
ON UPDATE NO ACTION)
ENGINE = InnoDB;
CREATE INDEX `fk_Archive_has_Language_Language1_idx` ON `erihis`.`Archive_has_Language` (`Language_idLanguage` ASC)
VISIBLE;
CREATE INDEX `fk_Archive_has_Language_Archive1_idx` ON `erihis`.`Archive_has_Language` (`Archive_idArchive` ASC,
`Archive_Archive_type_idArchive_type` ASC) VISIBLE;
-----
-- Table `erihis`.`Archive_has_Material`
-----
CREATE TABLE IF NOT EXISTS `erihis`.`Archive_has_Material` (
`Archive_idArchive` INT NOT NULL,
`Material_idMaterial` INT NOT NULL,
PRIMARY KEY (`Archive_idArchive`, `Material_idMaterial`),
CONSTRAINT `fk_Archive_has_Material_Archive1`
FOREIGN KEY (`Archive_idArchive`)
REFERENCES `erihis`.`Archive` (`Archive_id`)
ON DELETE NO ACTION
ON UPDATE NO ACTION,
CONSTRAINT `fk_Archive_has_Material_Material1`
FOREIGN KEY (`Material_idMaterial`)
REFERENCES `erihis`.`Material` (`Material_id`)
ON DELETE NO ACTION
ON UPDATE NO ACTION)
ENGINE = InnoDB;
CREATE INDEX `fk_Archive_has_Material_Material1_idx` ON `erihis`.`Archive_has_Material` (`Material_idMaterial` ASC) VISIBLE;
CREATE INDEX `fk_Archive_has_Material_Archive1_idx` ON `erihis`.`Archive_has_Material` (`Archive_idArchive` ASC) VISIBLE;
-----
-- Table `erihis`.`Archive_has_Subject`
-----
CREATE TABLE IF NOT EXISTS `erihis`.`Archive_has_Subject` (
`Archive_idArchive` INT NOT NULL,
`Subject_idSubject` INT NOT NULL,
PRIMARY KEY (`Archive_idArchive`, `Subject_idSubject`),
CONSTRAINT `fk_Archive_has_Subject_Archive1`
FOREIGN KEY (`Archive_idArchive`)

```

```

REFERENCES `erihis`.`Archive` (`Archive_id`)
ON DELETE NO ACTION
ON UPDATE NO ACTION,
CONSTRAINT `fk_Archive_has_Subject_Subject1`
FOREIGN KEY (`Subject_idSubject`)
REFERENCES `erihis`.`Subject` (`Subject_id`)
ON DELETE NO ACTION
ON UPDATE NO ACTION)
ENGINE = InnoDB;
CREATE INDEX `fk_Archive_has_Subject_Subject1_idx` ON `erihis`.`Archive_has_Subject` (`Subject_idSubject` ASC) VISIBLE;
CREATE INDEX `fk_Archive_has_Subject_Archive1_idx` ON `erihis`.`Archive_has_Subject` (`Archive_idArchive` ASC) VISIBLE;
-----
-- Table `erihis`.`Archive_type`
-----
CREATE TABLE IF NOT EXISTS `erihis`.`Archive_type` (
  `idArchive_type` INT NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `type` VARCHAR(45) NOT NULL COMMENT 'type can be only: Physical archive, Digital archive, Both',
  PRIMARY KEY (`idArchive_type`))
ENGINE = InnoDB;
-----
-- Table `erihis`.`Category_of_technique`
-----
CREATE TABLE IF NOT EXISTS `erihis`.`Category_of_technique` (
  `Cat_technique_id` INT NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `short name` VARCHAR(45) NOT NULL,
  `description` VARCHAR(2048) NULL,
  `Platform_idPlatform` INT NOT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`Cat_technique_id`, `Platform_idPlatform`),
  CONSTRAINT `fk_Category_of_technique_Platform1`
  FOREIGN KEY (`Platform_idPlatform`)
  REFERENCES `erihis`.`Platform` (`Platform_id`)
  ON DELETE NO ACTION
  ON UPDATE NO ACTION)
ENGINE = InnoDB;
CREATE INDEX `fk_Category_of_technique_Platform1_idx` ON `erihis`.`Category_of_technique` (`Platform_idPlatform` ASC) VISIBLE;
-----
-- Table `erihis`.`Competence`
-----
CREATE TABLE IF NOT EXISTS `erihis`.`Competence` (
  `Competence_id` INT NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `name` VARCHAR(45) NOT NULL COMMENT 'name can be only: Restoration, Conservation, Prevention, Documentation, Study,
Education',
  PRIMARY KEY (`Competence_id`))

```

```

ENGINE = InnoDB;
-----
-- Table `erihis`.`Field_of_application`
-----
CREATE TABLE IF NOT EXISTS `erihis`.`Field_of_application` (
  `Field_of_applicationid` INT NOT NULL,
  `type` VARCHAR(128) NOT NULL,
  `subtype` VARCHAR(128) NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`Field_of_applicationid`))
ENGINE = InnoDB;
-----
-- Table `erihis`.`Language`
-----
CREATE TABLE IF NOT EXISTS `erihis`.`Language` (
  `Language_id` INT NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `name` VARCHAR(45) NOT NULL COMMENT 'Name can be: Dutch, French, German, English, Italian, Romanian, Spanish, Swedish,
Other',
  PRIMARY KEY (`Language_id`))
ENGINE = InnoDB;
-----
-- Table `erihis`.`Material`
-----
CREATE TABLE IF NOT EXISTS `erihis`.`Material` (
  `Material_id` INT NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `type` VARCHAR(128) NOT NULL COMMENT 'Type can be only: Organic, Inorganic, Both, Other',
  `subtype` VARCHAR(128) NULL COMMENT 'Subtype can be only: -if type is "organic": wood, paper, textiles, animal parts, binding
media, glues, vanishes; -if type is "inorganic": stone, ceramic, glass, metal and metallurgical by-products',
  PRIMARY KEY (`Material_id`))
ENGINE = InnoDB;
-----
-- Table `erihis`.`Organizational_entity`
-----
CREATE TABLE IF NOT EXISTS `erihis`.`Organizational_entity` (
  `Organizational_entity_id` INT NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `name_en` VARCHAR(256) NOT NULL COMMENT 'name_en id the English name',
  `type` VARCHAR(45) NULL COMMENT 'type=category The following values are permitted: Main Institution, Department,
Laboratory, Virtual entity',
  `authorized name` VARCHAR(512) NULL,
  `acronym` VARCHAR(45) NULL,
  `legal status` VARCHAR(45) NULL,
  `legal address` VARCHAR(45) NULL,
  `service address` VARCHAR(45) NULL COMMENT 'Type has only three possible values: MI, D, L',
  `city` VARCHAR(45) NULL,
  `country` VARCHAR(45) NOT NULL,

```

```

`region` VARCHAR(45) NULL,
`postal code` VARCHAR(45) NULL,
`phone` VARCHAR(45) NULL,
`description` VARCHAR(6144) NULL,
`website` VARCHAR(45) NULL,
`gps link` VARCHAR(120) NULL,
`virtual` TINYINT(1) NULL,
`facility` VARCHAR(45) NULL,
PRIMARY KEY (`Organizational_entity_id`))
ENGINE = InnoDB;
-----
-- Table `erihis`.`Organizational_entity_has_Organizational_entity`
-----
CREATE TABLE IF NOT EXISTS `erihis`.`Organizational_entity_has_Organizational_entity` (
  `Organizational_entity_idOrganizational_entity` INT NOT NULL,
  `Organizational_entity_idOrganizational_entity1` INT NOT NULL,
  `partOf` VARCHAR(45) NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`Organizational_entity_idOrganizational_entity`, `Organizational_entity_idOrganizational_entity1`),
  CONSTRAINT `fk_Organizational_entity_has_Organizational_entity_Organizati1`
    FOREIGN KEY (`Organizational_entity_idOrganizational_entity`)
    REFERENCES `erihis`.`Organizational_entity` (`Organizational_entity_id`)
    ON DELETE NO ACTION
    ON UPDATE NO ACTION,
  CONSTRAINT `fk_Organizational_entity_has_Organizational_entity_Organizati2`
    FOREIGN KEY (`Organizational_entity_idOrganizational_entity1`)
    REFERENCES `erihis`.`Organizational_entity` (`Organizational_entity_id`)
    ON DELETE NO ACTION
    ON UPDATE NO ACTION)
ENGINE = InnoDB;
CREATE INDEX `fk_Organizational_entity_has_Organizational_entity_Organiza_idx` ON
`erihis`.`Organizational_entity_has_Organizational_entity` (`Organizational_entity_idOrganizational_entity1` ASC) VISIBLE;
CREATE INDEX `fk_Organizational_entity_has_Organizational_entity_Organiza_idx1` ON
`erihis`.`Organizational_entity_has_Organizational_entity` (`Organizational_entity_idOrganizational_entity` ASC) VISIBLE;
-----
-- Table `erihis`.`Organizational_entity_has_Provider`
-----
CREATE TABLE IF NOT EXISTS `erihis`.`Organizational_entity_has_Provider` (
  `Organizational_entity_idOrganizational_entity` INT NOT NULL,
  `Provider_idProvider` INT NOT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`Organizational_entity_idOrganizational_entity`, `Provider_idProvider`),
  CONSTRAINT `fk_Organizational_entity_has_Provider_Organizational_entity1`

```

```

FOREIGN KEY (`Organizational_entity_idOrganizational_entity`)
REFERENCES `erihs`.`Organizational_entity` (`Organizational_entity_id`)
ON DELETE NO ACTION
ON UPDATE NO ACTION,
CONSTRAINT `fk_Organizational_entity_has_Provider_Provider1`
FOREIGN KEY (`Provider_idProvider`)
REFERENCES `erihs`.`Provider` (`Provider_id`)
ON DELETE NO ACTION
ON UPDATE NO ACTION)
ENGINE = InnoDB;
CREATE INDEX `fk_Organizational_entity_has_Provider_Provider1_idx` ON `erihs`.`Organizational_entity_has_Provider`
(`Provider_idProvider` ASC) VISIBLE;
CREATE INDEX `fk_Organizational_entity_has_Provider_Organizational_entity_idx` ON
`erihs`.`Organizational_entity_has_Provider` (`Organizational_entity_idOrganizational_entity` ASC) VISIBLE;
-----
-- Table `erihs`.`Person`
-----
CREATE TABLE IF NOT EXISTS `erihs`.`Person` (
  `Person_id` INT NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `name` VARCHAR(45) NOT NULL,
  `name1` VARCHAR(45) NULL,
  `surname` VARCHAR(45) NOT NULL,
  `phone` VARCHAR(45) NULL,
  `email` VARCHAR(45) NULL,
  `Organizational_entity_idOrganizational_entity` INT NOT NULL,
  `role` VARCHAR(15) NOT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`Person_id`),
  CONSTRAINT `fk_Person_Organizational_entity1`
FOREIGN KEY (`Organizational_entity_idOrganizational_entity`)
REFERENCES `erihs`.`Organizational_entity` (`Organizational_entity_id`)
ON DELETE NO ACTION
ON UPDATE NO ACTION)
ENGINE = InnoDB;
CREATE INDEX `fk_Person_Organizational_entity1_idx` ON `erihs`.`Person` (`Organizational_entity_idOrganizational_entity` ASC)
VISIBLE;
-----
-- Table `erihs`.`Person_has_Archive`
-----
CREATE TABLE IF NOT EXISTS `erihs`.`Person_has_Archive` (
  `Person_idPerson` INT NOT NULL,
  `Archive_idArchive` INT NOT NULL,
  `Archive_Archive_type_idArchive_type` INT NOT NULL,

```

```

PRIMARY KEY (`Person_idPerson`, `Archive_idArchive`, `Archive_Archive_type_idArchive_type`),
CONSTRAINT `fk_Person_has_Archive_Person1`
  FOREIGN KEY (`Person_idPerson`)
  REFERENCES `erihis`.`Person` (`Person_id`)
  ON DELETE NO ACTION
  ON UPDATE NO ACTION,
CONSTRAINT `fk_Person_has_Archive_Archive1`
  FOREIGN KEY (`Archive_idArchive`, `Archive_Archive_type_idArchive_type`)
  REFERENCES `erihis`.`Archive` (`Archive_id`, `Archive_type_idArchive_type`)
  ON DELETE NO ACTION
  ON UPDATE NO ACTION)
ENGINE = InnoDB;
CREATE INDEX `fk_Person_has_Archive_Archive1_idx` ON `erihis`.`Person_has_Archive` (`Archive_idArchive` ASC,
`Archive_Archive_type_idArchive_type` ASC) VISIBLE;
CREATE INDEX `fk_Person_has_Archive_Person1_idx` ON `erihis`.`Person_has_Archive` (`Person_idPerson` ASC) VISIBLE;
-----
-- Table `erihis`.`Person_has_Provider`
-----
CREATE TABLE IF NOT EXISTS `erihis`.`Person_has_Provider` (
  `Person_idPerson` INT NOT NULL,
  `Provider_idProvider` INT NOT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`Person_idPerson`, `Provider_idProvider`),
  CONSTRAINT `fk_Person_has_Provider_Person1`
    FOREIGN KEY (`Person_idPerson`)
    REFERENCES `erihis`.`Person` (`Person_id`)
    ON DELETE NO ACTION
    ON UPDATE NO ACTION,
  CONSTRAINT `fk_Person_has_Provider_Provider1`
    FOREIGN KEY (`Provider_idProvider`)
    REFERENCES `erihis`.`Provider` (`Provider_id`)
    ON DELETE NO ACTION
    ON UPDATE NO ACTION)
ENGINE = InnoDB;
CREATE INDEX `fk_Person_has_Provider_Provider1_idx` ON `erihis`.`Person_has_Provider` (`Provider_idProvider` ASC) VISIBLE;
CREATE INDEX `fk_Person_has_Provider_Person1_idx` ON `erihis`.`Person_has_Provider` (`Person_idPerson` ASC) VISIBLE;
-----
-- Table `erihis`.`Person_has_Technique`
-----
CREATE TABLE IF NOT EXISTS `erihis`.`Person_has_Technique` (
  `Person_idPerson` INT NOT NULL,
  `Technique_idTechnique` INT NOT NULL,

```

```

PRIMARY KEY (`Person_idPerson`, `Technique_idTechnique`),
CONSTRAINT `fk_Person_has_Technique_Person1`
  FOREIGN KEY (`Person_idPerson`)
  REFERENCES `erihis`.`Person` (`Person_id`)
  ON DELETE NO ACTION
  ON UPDATE NO ACTION,
CONSTRAINT `fk_Person_has_Technique_Technique1`
  FOREIGN KEY (`Technique_idTechnique`)
  REFERENCES `erihis`.`Technique` (`Technique_id`)
  ON DELETE NO ACTION
  ON UPDATE NO ACTION)
ENGINE = InnoDB;
CREATE INDEX `fk_Person_has_Technique_Technique1_idx` ON `erihis`.`Person_has_Technique` (`Technique_idTechnique` ASC)
VISIBLE;
CREATE INDEX `fk_Person_has_Technique_Person1_idx` ON `erihis`.`Person_has_Technique` (`Person_idPerson` ASC) VISIBLE;
-----
-- Table `erihis`.`Platform`
-----
CREATE TABLE IF NOT EXISTS `erihis`.`Platform` (
  `Platform_id` INT NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `name` VARCHAR(45) NOT NULL,
  `description` VARCHAR(512) NULL,
  `Person_idPerson` INT NOT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`Platform_id`, `Person_idPerson`),
  CONSTRAINT `fk_Platform_Person1`
    FOREIGN KEY (`Person_idPerson`)
    REFERENCES `erihis`.`Person` (`Person_id`)
    ON DELETE NO ACTION
    ON UPDATE NO ACTION)
ENGINE = InnoDB;
CREATE INDEX `fk_Platform_Person1_idx` ON `erihis`.`Platform` (`Person_idPerson` ASC) VISIBLE;
-----
-- Table `erihis`.`Provider`
-----
CREATE TABLE IF NOT EXISTS `erihis`.`Provider` (
  `Provider_id` INT NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `Main_Institution1` VARCHAR(45) NULL,
  `Main_Institution2` VARCHAR(45) NULL,
  `Main_Institution3` VARCHAR(45) NULL,
  `Department1` VARCHAR(45) NULL,
  `Department2` VARCHAR(45) NULL,

```

```

`Department3` VARCHAR(45) NULL,
`Laboratory1` VARCHAR(45) NULL,
`Laboratory2` VARCHAR(45) NULL,
`Laboratory3` VARCHAR(45) NULL,
`Facility` VARCHAR(45) NULL,
PRIMARY KEY (`Provider_id`))
ENGINE = InnoDB;
-----
-- Table `erihis`.`Service`
-----
CREATE TABLE IF NOT EXISTS `erihis`.`Service` (
  `Service_id` INT NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `name` VARCHAR(256) NOT NULL,
  `id_provider` VARCHAR(45) NOT NULL COMMENT 'Provider's name is obtained joining the acronyms of the three organisational
entities',
  `description` VARCHAR(2048) NULL,
  `CATtechnique` VARCHAR(128) NULL,
  `technique` VARCHAR(45) NULL,
  `tool` INT NULL,
  `contact_person1` INT NOT NULL,
  `contact_person2` VARCHAR(45) NULL,
  `contact_person3` INT NOT NULL,
  `contact_person4` VARCHAR(45) NULL,
  `idArchive` INT NULL,
  `Platform_idPlatform` INT NULL,
  `Service_name` VARCHAR(45) NULL,
  `Analysis_name` VARCHAR(45) NULL,
PRIMARY KEY (`Service_id`, `contact_person1`),
CONSTRAINT `fk_Service_Person`
  FOREIGN KEY (`contact_person1`)
  REFERENCES `erihis`.`Person` (`Person_id`)
  ON DELETE NO ACTION
  ON UPDATE NO ACTION,
CONSTRAINT `fk_Service_Archive1`
  FOREIGN KEY (`idArchive`)
  REFERENCES `erihis`.`Archive` (`Archive_id`)
  ON DELETE NO ACTION
  ON UPDATE NO ACTION,
CONSTRAINT `fk_Service_Platform1`

```

```

FOREIGN KEY (`Platform_idPlatform`, `contact_person3`)
REFERENCES `erihis`.`Platform` (`Platform_id`, `Person_idPerson`)
ON DELETE NO ACTION
ON UPDATE NO ACTION
ENGINE = InnoDB;
CREATE INDEX `fk_Service_Person_idx` ON `erihis`.`Service` (`contact_person1` ASC) VISIBLE;
CREATE INDEX `fk_Service_Archive1_idx` ON `erihis`.`Service` (`idArchive` ASC) VISIBLE;
CREATE INDEX `fk_Service_Platform1_idx` ON `erihis`.`Service` (`Platform_idPlatform` ASC, `contact_person3` ASC) VISIBLE;
-----
-- Table `erihis`.`Subject`
-----
CREATE TABLE IF NOT EXISTS `erihis`.`Subject` (
  `Subject_id` INT NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `type` VARCHAR(128) NOT NULL COMMENT 'type can be: Cultural heritage, Natural heritage, Cultural and natural heritage',
  `subtype` VARCHAR(128) NULL COMMENT 'Subtype can be only: -if type is "cultural heritage": art, architecture, painting, decorative art, sculpture, textile, mosaic, archaeological object and site, Film, photo, musical instrument, manuscript, demo anthropologic object, other; -if type is "natural heritage": mineral, animal product, taxidermy collection, skeleton, fossil, shell, object in formalin, botanic collection, other',
  PRIMARY KEY (`Subject_id`))
ENGINE = InnoDB;
-----
-- Table `erihis`.`Technique`
-----
CREATE TABLE IF NOT EXISTS `erihis`.`Technique` (
  `Technique_id` INT NOT NULL,
  `name` VARCHAR(45) NULL,
  `short name` VARCHAR(45) NULL,
  `description` VARCHAR(4096) NULL,
  `notes` VARCHAR(2048) NULL,
  `link` VARCHAR(256) NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`Technique_id`))
ENGINE = InnoDB;
-----
-- Table `erihis`.`Technique_has_Category_of_technique`
-----
CREATE TABLE IF NOT EXISTS `erihis`.`Technique_has_Category_of_technique` (
  `Technique_idTechnique` INT NOT NULL,
  `Category_of_technique_idCategory of technique` INT NOT NULL,
  `Category_of_technique_Platform_idPlatform` INT NOT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`Technique_idTechnique`, `Category_of_technique_idCategory of technique`, `Category_of_technique_Platform_idPlatform`),
  CONSTRAINT `fk_Technique_has_Category_of_technique_Technique1`
  FOREIGN KEY (`Technique_idTechnique`)

```

```

REFERENCES `erihis`.`Technique` (`Technique_id`)
ON DELETE NO ACTION
ON UPDATE NO ACTION,
CONSTRAINT `fk_Technique_has_Category_of_technique_Category_of_technique1`
FOREIGN KEY (`Category_of_technique_idCategory of technique`, `Category_of_technique_Platform_idPlatform`)
REFERENCES `erihis`.`Category_of_technique` (`Cat_technique_id`, `Platform_idPlatform`)
ON DELETE NO ACTION
ON UPDATE NO ACTION)
ENGINE = InnoDB;
CREATE INDEX `fk_Technique_has_Category_of_technique_Category_of_technique_idx` ON
`erihis`.`Technique_has_Category_of_technique` (`Category_of_technique_idCategory of technique` ASC,
`Category_of_technique_Platform_idPlatform` ASC) VISIBLE;
CREATE INDEX `fk_Technique_has_Category_of_technique_Technique1_idx` ON `erihis`.`Technique_has_Category_of_technique`
(`Technique_idTechnique` ASC) VISIBLE;
-----
-- Table `erihis`.`Technique_has_foa`
-----
CREATE TABLE IF NOT EXISTS `erihis`.`Technique_has_foa` (
`Technique_idTechnique` INT NOT NULL,
`Field_of_applicationid` INT NOT NULL,
PRIMARY KEY (`Technique_idTechnique`, `Field_of_applicationid`),
CONSTRAINT `fk_Technique_has_foa_2`
FOREIGN KEY (`Field_of_applicationid`)
REFERENCES `erihis`.`Field_of_application` (`Field_of_applicationid`)
ON DELETE NO ACTION
ON UPDATE NO ACTION,
CONSTRAINT `fk_Technique_has_foa_1`
FOREIGN KEY (`Technique_idTechnique`)
REFERENCES `erihis`.`Technique` (`Technique_id`)
ON DELETE NO ACTION
ON UPDATE NO ACTION)
ENGINE = InnoDB;
CREATE INDEX `fk_Technique_has_foa_2_idx` ON `erihis`.`Technique_has_foa` (`Field_of_applicationid` ASC) VISIBLE;
-----
-- Table `erihis`.`Technique_has_Material`
-----
CREATE TABLE IF NOT EXISTS `erihis`.`Technique_has_Material` (
`Technique_idTechnique` INT NOT NULL,
`Material_idMaterial` INT NOT NULL,
PRIMARY KEY (`Technique_idTechnique`, `Material_idMaterial`),
CONSTRAINT `fk_Archive_has_Material_Material10`
FOREIGN KEY (`Material_idMaterial`)

```

```

REFERENCES `erihis`.`Material` (`Material_id`)
ON DELETE NO ACTION
ON UPDATE NO ACTION,
CONSTRAINT `fk_Technique_has_Material_1`
FOREIGN KEY (`Technique_idTechnique`)
REFERENCES `erihis`.`Technique` (`Technique_id`)
ON DELETE NO ACTION
ON UPDATE NO ACTION)
ENGINE = InnoDB;
CREATE INDEX `fk_Archive_has_Material_Material1_idx` ON `erihis`.`Technique_has_Material` (`Material_idMaterial` ASC)
VISIBLE;
-----
-- Table `erihis`.`Technique_has_tools`
-----
CREATE TABLE IF NOT EXISTS `erihis`.`Technique_has_tools` (
  `IdTool` INT NOT NULL,
  `IdTechnique` INT NOT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`IdTool`, `IdTechnique`),
  CONSTRAINT `fkTools`
  FOREIGN KEY (`IdTool`)
  REFERENCES `erihis`.`Tool` (`idtool`)
  ON DELETE NO ACTION
  ON UPDATE NO ACTION,
  CONSTRAINT `fkTechnique`
  FOREIGN KEY (`IdTechnique`)
  REFERENCES `erihis`.`Technique` (`Technique_id`)
  ON DELETE NO ACTION
  ON UPDATE NO ACTION)
ENGINE = InnoDB;
CREATE INDEX `fkTechnique_idx` ON `erihis`.`Technique_has_tools` (`IdTechnique` ASC) VISIBLE;
-----
-- Table `erihis`.`Tool`
-----
CREATE TABLE IF NOT EXISTS `erihis`.`Tool` (
  `idtool` INT NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `name` VARCHAR(256) NULL,
  `description` VARCHAR(4096) NULL,
  `potential results` VARCHAR(4096) NULL,
  `Platform_idPlatform` INT NOT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`idtool`, `Platform_idPlatform`),
  CONSTRAINT `fk_Platform_idPlatform`

```

```

FOREIGN KEY (`Platform_idPlatform`)
REFERENCES `erihis`.`Platform` (`Platform_id`)
ON DELETE NO ACTION
ON UPDATE NO ACTION)
ENGINE = InnoDB;
-----
-- Table `erihis`.`tool_has_Service`
-----
CREATE TABLE IF NOT EXISTS `erihis`.`tool_has_Service` (
`tool_idtool` INT NOT NULL,
`Service_idService` INT NOT NULL,
`Service_Person_idPerson` INT NOT NULL,
PRIMARY KEY (`tool_idtool`, `Service_idService`, `Service_Person_idPerson`),
CONSTRAINT `fk_tool_has_Service_tool1`
FOREIGN KEY (`tool_idtool`)
REFERENCES `erihis`.`Tool` (`idtool`)
ON DELETE NO ACTION
ON UPDATE NO ACTION,
CONSTRAINT `fk_tool_has_Service_Service1`
FOREIGN KEY (`Service_idService`, `Service_Person_idPerson`)
REFERENCES `erihis`.`Service` (`Service_id`, `contact_person1`)
ON DELETE NO ACTION
ON UPDATE NO ACTION)
ENGINE = InnoDB;
CREATE INDEX `fk_tool_has_Service_Service1_idx` ON `erihis`.`tool_has_Service` (`Service_idService` ASC, `Service_Person_idPerson`
ASC) VISIBLE;
CREATE INDEX `fk_tool_has_Service_tool1_idx` ON `erihis`.`tool_has_Service` (`tool_idtool` ASC) VISIBLE;
-----
-- Table `erihis`.`type_of_data`
-----
CREATE TABLE IF NOT EXISTS `erihis`.`type_of_data` (
`idtype_of_data` INT NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
`type` VARCHAR(64) NOT NULL COMMENT 'type can be only: Audiovisual material, Documentation, Sample collection, Data set,
Visual material, Publication, Reference material, Everything',
`subtype` VARCHAR(45) NULL COMMENT 'Subtype can be:-if type is documentation: scientific report, reference material,
bibliography, analytic study, other; -if type is audiovisual: video recording, audio recording, film; -if visual material: photo, drawing,
map, picture, poster',
PRIMARY KEY (`idtype_of_data`))
ENGINE = InnoDB;
-----
-- Table `erihis`.`type_of_data_has_Archive`
-----
CREATE TABLE IF NOT EXISTS `erihis`.`type_of_data_has_Archive` (

```

```

`type_of_data_idtype_of_data` INT NOT NULL,
`Archive_idArchive` INT NOT NULL,
PRIMARY KEY (`type_of_data_idtype_of_data`, `Archive_idArchive`),
CONSTRAINT `fk_type_of_data_has_Archive_type_of_data1`
FOREIGN KEY (`type_of_data_idtype_of_data`)
REFERENCES `erihs`.`type_of_data` (`idtype_of_data`)
ON DELETE NO ACTION
ON UPDATE NO ACTION,
CONSTRAINT `fk_type_of_data_has_Archive_Archive1`
FOREIGN KEY (`Archive_idArchive`)
REFERENCES `erihs`.`Archive` (`Archive_id`)
ON DELETE NO ACTION
ON UPDATE NO ACTION)
ENGINE = InnoDB;
CREATE INDEX `fk_type_of_data_has_Archive_Archive1_idx` ON `erihs`.`type_of_data_has_Archive` (`Archive_idArchive` ASC)
VISIBLE;
CREATE INDEX `fk_type_of_data_has_Archive_type_of_data1_idx` ON `erihs`.`type_of_data_has_Archive`
(`type_of_data_idtype_of_data` ASC) VISIBLE;
SET SQL_MODE=@OLD_SQL_MODE;
SET FOREIGN_KEY_CHECKS=@OLD_FOREIGN_KEY_CHECKS;
SET UNIQUE_CHECKS=@OLD_UNIQUE_CHECKS;

```

Annex5. SQL queries

List of Techniques, ordered by Facilities acronym

```

SELECT o4.acronym as 'Facility',
tec.name as 'technique',
cot.`short name` as 'category of technique',
tool.name as 'tool',
se.Analysis_name, pla.name as 'platform'
FROM
erihs.Provider as p, erihs.Organizational_entity as o,
erihs.Organizational_entity as o1, erihs.Organizational_entity as o3,
erihs.Organizational_entity as o4, erihs.Service as se,
erihs.Category_of_technique as cot, erihs.Technique as tec,
erihs.Tool as tool, erihs.Platform as pla
WHERE
se.id_provider=p.Provider_id
and p.Main_Institution1=o.Organizational_entity_id
and p.Department1=o1.Organizational_entity_id
and p.Laboratory1=o3.Organizational_entity_id
and cot.Cat_technique_id=se.id_CatTechnique
and tec.Technique_id=se.technique
and tool.idtool=se.tool

```

```

and o4.Organizational_entity_id =p.facility
and se.Platform_IdPlatform=pla.Platform_id
ORDER BY `Facility`
    
```

List of Services

```

SELECT o.acronym as 'main inst.', o1.acronym as 'department', o3.acronym as 'laboratory', pn.name as 'contact
name',
pn.surname as 'contact surname',
cot.`short name` as 'category of techninque',
tec.name as 'technique', tool.name as 'tool'

FROM
erihs.Provider as p, erihs.Organizational_entity as o,
erihs.Organizational_entity as o1, erihs.Organizational_entity as o3,
erihs.Person_has_Provider as pe, erihs.Person as pn,
erihs.Service as se, erihs.Category_of_technique as cot,
erihs.Tool as tool, erihs.Technique as tec

WHERE
se.id_provider=p.Provider_id and
pe.Provider_idProvider=p.Provider_id and
pn.Person_id=pe.Person_idPerson and
p.Main_Institution1=o.Organizational_entity_id and p.Department1=o1.Organizational_entity_id
and p.Laboratory1=o3.Organizational_entity_id
and cot.Cat_technique_id=se.id_CatTechnique
and tec.Technique_id=se.technique
and tool.idtool=se.tool
ORDER BY `main inst`,`department`,`laboratory`;
    
```

Annex 6. Templates created for each entity

Template person

Label	Field
ID	identifier
Name	string
Surname	
Phone	string
Email	string
MI	(reverse link: MI)
D	(reverse link D)
L	reverse link L
provide archive	reverse link (tool)
provide tool	reverse link (tool)

Template Main Institution

Label	Field
ID	identifier
category	string
Authorized form of the name of the institution	string
English name	string
Acronym	string
Legal status	controlled vocabulary (public body, private body, non-profit organisation, SME, international organisation, international organisation of European interest, research organisation, secondary education establishment, higher education establishment)
History of the institution	long text
Description	long text
Website	link
contact person	reverse link (person)
Location	reverse link (location)

Template Department

Label	Field	Description
ID	string	
category		department
Authorized form of the name of the department		name in the original language
English name	string	name in English
ACRONYM		Acronym
Description	long-text	description of the department
Website	link	website
Contact person	reverse link (person)	contact person
Location	reverse link (location)	location

Template Laboratory

Label	Field	Description
-------	-------	-------------

ID	string	
Category	text	laboratory
Authorized form of the name of the lab	text	name in the original language
English name	string	name in English
Acronym	text	acronym
Description	long-text	description of the department
Website	link	<u>website</u>
Contact person	reverse link (person)	contact person
Location	reverse link (location)	location

Template Virtual facility

Label	Field	Description
ID	string	
category	text	Virtual facility / project / collaboration
Authorized form of the name of the lab	Text	name in the original language
English name	string	name in English
Acronym	Text	acronym
Description	long-text	description of the department
Website	link	<u>website</u>
Contact person	reverse link (person)	contact person

Template Location

Label	field	description
ID	string	
Address	string	address
Postal code	string	postal code
City	string	city
Country	string	country
Link to the google map	link	<u>link to the google map</u>

Template ARCHLAB Archive

Label	field type	description
Archive		
ID	string	the identifier used to indicate the service
Platform	controlled vocabulary	ARCHLAB
Title of the Archive		title of the archive (original language)
English title		title of the archive in English
Acronym		
Type	controlled vocabulary	physical archive / digital archive / both
Description	long text	detailed description of the archive
Producer subject(s)	string	here indicate the subject who produces the archival documentation
Competence	controlled vocabulary	restoration, conservation, prevention, documentation, study, education
Type of data	controlled vocabulary	everything, audiovisual materials, documentation, sample collection, data set, visual materials, publications, reference materials
		if documentation: scientific report, reference material, bibliography, analytic study, ...
		if audiovisual: video recordings, audio recordings, film
		if visual materials: photo, drawing, map, picture, poster
Subject	controlled vocabulary	cultural heritage / natural heritage / both
		if cultural heritage: art, architecture, painting, decorative arts, sculpture, textile, mosaics, archaeological object and site, film, photo, musical instrument, manuscript, demo anthropologic object, other (free search)
		if natural heritage: Mineral, Animal product, Taxidermy collection, Skeleton, Fossil, Shell, Object in formalin, Botanic collection, other
Material	controlled vocabulary	organic / inorganic / both
		in case organic: wood, paper, textiles, animal parts, binding media, glues, varnishes
		in case inorganic: stone, ceramic (clay, mud brick, terracotta, earthenware, stoneware, porcelain), glass, metal and metallurgical By-Products
Archival dates	string	date of the documentation preserved in the archive - exact dates (1970-1992), open date (1970-), centuries (19th)
Language	controlled vocabulary	Dutch, French, German, English, Italian, Romanian, Spanish, Swedish, other
Main institution	reverse link (MI)	here is the name of the main institution

Department	reverse link (D)	here is the name of department
Laboratory	reverse link (I)	here is the name of laboratory
Contact person	reverse link (person)	the contact person of the actor that provides the service (name lastname)
Online inventory	link	
Other online resources	link	
Keywords	controlled vocabulary	
Notes / warning	long text	e.g. "Metals and magnetic materials can not be studied".

Template FIXLAB technique

Label	field type	description
ID	string	
Platform	controlled vocabulary	FIXLAB
Category of technique	controlled vocabulary	Imaging (multiscale and multispectral), Microscopies, X-ray techniques, Optical spectroscopies, Molecular spectroscopies, Molecular analysis, Mass spectrometries, Biological analysis, Ion Beam Analysis techniques, Neutron techniques, Dating, Physical characterization, Thermal characterization, Accelerated Ageing tests, Environmental parameters measurements, Conservation techniques and preparation methods
Name	string	title of the technique (acronym)
Description	long text	detailed description of the technique
Field of application	controlled vocabulary	cultural heritage / natural heritage / both
	controlled vocabulary	if cultural heritage: art, architecture, painting, decorative arts, sculpture, textile, mosaics, archaeological object and site, film, photo, musical instrument, manuscript, papyrus demo anthropologic object, other (free search)
	controlled vocabulary	if natural heritage: Mineral, Animal product, Taxidermy collection, Skeleton, Fossil, Shell, Object in formalin, Botanic collection, other
Material	controlled vocabulary	organic / inorganic / both / free search
	controlled vocabulary	in case organic: wood, paper, textiles, animal parts, binding media, glues, varnishes
	controlled vocabulary	in case inorganic: stone, ceramic (clay, mud brick, terracotta, earthenware, stoneware, porcelain), glass, metal and metallurgical By-Products, pigment
Main institution	reverse link (MI)	here is the name of the main institution
Department	reverse link (D)	here is the name of department
Laboratory	reverse link (L)	here is the name of laboratory

Contact person	reverse link (person)	the contact person of the actor that provides the service (name lastname)
Other online resources	link	
Notes / warning	long text	e.g. "Metals and magnetic materials can not be studied".

Template MOLAB technique

Label	field	description
Technique		
ID	string	identifier
Platform	MOLAB	name of the platform
Category of technique	controlled vocabulary	Point analysis (close range)/ (Multi/hyper spectral) imaging/mapping (close range)/ 2D/3D analysis (close range)/ Remote sensing
Name	text	name of the technique
Description	long text	description of the technique
Fields of application	controlled vocabulary	cultural heritage; natural heritage, both
		if cultural heritage: art, architecture, painting, decorative arts, sculpture, textile, mosaics, archaeological object and site, film, photo, musical instrument, manuscript, papyrus, demo anthropologic object, other (free search)
		if natural heritage: Mineral, Animal product, Taxidermy collection, Skeleton, Fossil, Shell, Object in formalin, Botanic collection, other
Material	controlled vocabulary	Organic; inorganic; both
		in case organic: wood, paper, textiles, animal parts, binding media, glues, varnishes
		in case inorganic: stone, ceramic (clay, mud brick, terracotta, earthenware, stoneware, porcelain), glass, metal and metallurgical By-Products, pigment
Main institution	reverse link (MI)	here is the name of the main institution
Department	reverse link (D)	here is the name of department
Laboratory	reverse link (I)	here is the name of laboratory
Contact person	reverse link (person)	the contact person of the actor that provides the service (name lastname)
Other online resources	link	links to online resources (website, article, etc.)
Notes / warning	long text	e.g. "Metals and magnetic materials can not be studied".

Template Tool

Label	field	description
ID	string	identifier
Name	string	Name of the tool

Technical description	long text	Technical description of the tool
Potential results	long text	Description of the potential results <i>(please describe exhaustively and precisely the potential results: it will be very useful for users for understanding and choosing your technique)</i>
Contact person	reverse link (person)	Contact person of the tool

Providers have been encouraged to add new terms in the fields “Fields of application” and “Material” to start creating a specific thesaurus for E-RIHS.